

Metal ion catalysis in model electron transfer reactions[†]

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Manuscript received 19 September 2002

The reactions of a phenazine dye, methylene blue with sulfhydryl substrates have been investigated in acidic medium in presence of metal ions Cu^{II} and Ru^{III}. The substrates are the functional parts of active biomolecules and our investigation reveals that the kinetics of these reactions are appreciably influenced by the environmental and the steric factors. The mechanistic conclusions partly explain the complexity of biochemical processes involving these substrates.

The molecular geometry plays a crucial role in drawing important conclusions about molecular properties and in understanding of reaction dynamics¹. In some enzymatic reactions, the catalytic site of the enzymes such as yeast enolase, nitrite reductase is specifically affected by metal ions Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cu^{II} added along with Mg^{II}^{2,3}. Zinc is known to be functional in about 300 enzymes representing all subgroups of the enzyme classification⁴. The most distinctive feature in the structure of heme thiolate proteins is the coordination of a thiolate anion, from proximal cysteine residue, to the heme iron as a fifth ligand⁵. In proteins such as zinc-finger peptide, cysteine and histidine side-chains are tetrahedrally coordinated to a central Zn^{II} ion⁶. Thus, the reactivity of sulfur centre depends upon the environment, its oxidation state and the presence of specific metal ions⁷⁻¹² and it appears that electron transfer reactions involving metal ion-thiol interaction may be helpful in understanding the chemistry of metalloenzymes.

Nature of the reaction system :

The participation of metal ions in regulation of mitochondrial electron transfer reactions is the basic component of cellular energy transduction which is regarded as a three-fold process : (i) the release of energy by electron flow from more electronegative to more electropositive redox couples, (ii) the conversion of this electromotive force into a promotive force, and (iii) the use of promotive force to cause activating conformational changes in the membrane bound enzyme which mediates ATP synthesis. The routes involved are H-atom transfer, (i) mediated by nucleotide or quinonoid molecules (two electron movement) and (ii) simple electron transfer between metal protein centres (one electron transfer). Metal complexes also play a crucial role in a wide variety of processes including oxygen transport¹³, digestion¹⁴ and gene transcription^{15,16}.

Objectives :

The thiol-methylene blue (MB) interaction is catalyzed by Cu^{II} and Ru^{III}¹⁷⁻²⁰ and our investigations on Cu^{II}-catalyzed oxidation of cysteine show that Zn^{II} considerably enhances the activity of Cu^{II}²¹ which may perhaps involve the intramolecular excitation energy transfer²². The following objectives have received focus :

[A] Kinetic studies on the interaction of biological active thiols such as cysteine (III), 2-mercaptoethylamine (functional part of coenzyme A, IV), mercaptoacetic acid and *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid (a model of papain, V) with the electron receptor MB, a phenazine dye [phenothiazin-5-ium-3,7-bis(dimethylamino)chloride, I].

[B] Catalysis by individual and mixed metal ions, such as Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Ru^{III}.

[C] Kinetic influence of the neighbouring groups such as NH₂, COOH, R etc. of the substrates. It may be mentioned that in the oxidation of thioethers, the neighbouring groups act catalytically through transient bond formation between radical cationic intermediates and electron lone-pair carrying functional groups such as O, N, S, P and Se²³. The neighbouring groups affect the formation and nature of the transient species²⁴.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

With this background, the kinetic investigations on the oxidation of some sulfhydryl substrates, which are model electron receptors in biological systems, with methylene blue in acidic medium have been made²⁵⁻²⁷ and those studied in presence of metal ions such as Cu^{II} and Ru^{III} have been summarized in this communication.

Results

Oxidation of cysteine hydrochloride catalysed by Cu^{II} :

The order of reaction in MB is found to be one at higher [MB] (*ca.* $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) while at lower concentrations, the order in MB changes to half (Table 1). The runs were made under anaerobic conditions and the absorbance of MB was measured (ATI-Unicam UV2-100 spectrophotometer). The reaction follows a first order kinetics in cysteine while the rate increases with increasing [H⁺] as its square-root. At higher concentration of hydrogen ion, the rate constant tends to attain a limiting value. The ionic strength of the system was maintained constant by adding the requisite amount of KCl. The rate increases on increasing the ionic strength but in presence of KCl, the order in MB shows a transition from unity to half which may be attributed to the metachromatic shift in methylene blue in presence of KCl²⁸. The rate increases linearly on increasing [Cu^{II}], but at higher concentrations of the catalyst, the rate almost levels off. The rate constant decreases on decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium but the addition of cysteine and leucobase did not influence the rate of reaction.

Table 1. Rate constant of the reaction of cysteine hydrochloride (excess) at different [MB]

[Cu] = $6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HCl] = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [CuSO₄] = $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, *I* = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, temp. = 35°

[MB] ×10 ⁵ M	k ₁ ×10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k ^{1/2} ×10 ⁶ mol ^{1/2} dm ^{-1/2} s ⁻¹
3.50	4.2	–
3.00	4.2	–
2.50	4.4	–
2.00	–	1.60
1.50	–	1.55
1.25	–	1.25

The activation parameters of the reaction were evaluated in the usual manner and Δ*H*^{*}, Δ*S*^{*} and Δ*G*^{*} are found to be 40.2 kJ mol⁻¹, -174.3 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 95.0 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Oxidation of 2-mercaptoethylamine hydrochloride (2-ME) catalyzed by Cu^{II} :

2-ME and methylene blue interact in a molar ratio 2 : 1 forming the corresponding disulfide and leucobase. The runs were made in methanol-water medium (5%, v/v) and in pres-

ence of sulfuric acid under anaerobic conditions. The order in MB is 3/2 at higher concentrations of 2-ME (*ca.* > $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) but at lower concentration of the substrate, the order in MB is found to be 2 (Table 2). The reaction follows a half-order kinetics in 2-ME. The rate decreases on increasing [MB] and at lower concentrations of methylene blue

Table 2. Rate constant at different [2-ME] under anaerobic conditions

[MB] = $3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, [H₂SO₄] = $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, [CuSO₄] = $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, *I* = $7.508 \times 10^{-2} M$, CH₃OH = 5% (v/v), temp. = 35°

[2-ME] ×10 ² mol dm ⁻³	k ₂ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k _{3/2} dm ^{1/2} mol ^{-1/2} s ⁻¹
0.750	10.6	–
0.904	14.6	–
1.040	–	9.2
1.260	–	9.8
1.430	–	11.5
1.800	–	11.7
2.200	–	13.3
2.500	–	13.8
2.870	–	15.9

(*ca.* < $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$), the order in MB changes to unity (Table 3). The rate first increases on increasing [H⁺] and attains a maximum value at $4.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate

Table 3. Rate constant at different [MB] under anaerobic conditions

[2-ME] = $1.8 \times 10^{-2} M$, [H₂SO₄] = $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, [CuSO₄] = $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, *I* = $7.508 \times 10^{-2} M$, CH₃OH = 5% (v/v), temp. = 35°

[MB] ×10 ⁵ M	k _{3/2} ×10 ² dm ^{1/2} mol ^{-1/2} s ⁻¹	k ₁ ×10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.00	–	8.1
1.45	–	7.1
2.00	14.1	–
2.50	12.4	–
3.00	11.7	–
3.50	10.1	–

increases on increasing [Cu^{II}] and attains a limiting value at higher concentrations. It has been noticed that the course of reaction is appreciably influenced by the timeperiod provided for the interaction of catalyst with the substrate. The rate constant gradually increases by increasing the time-span and attains a maximum value at 60 min. Δ*H*^{*}, Δ*S*^{*} and Δ*G*^{*} are found to be 26.8 kJ mol⁻¹, -179.3 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 82.0 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Oxidation of mercaptoacetic acid catalyzed by Ru^{III} :

The substrate and the oxidant in this case again interact in a molar ratio of 2 : 1 and the order with respect to mercaptoacetic acid (TGA) and methylene blue is unity (Table 4). The variation in [H⁺] did not influence the rate.

Table 4. Rate constant at different [TGA] and [MB] in presence of RuCl₃

[TGA] ×10 ³ M	k ₁ ×10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[MB] ×10 ⁵ M	k ₁ ×10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
5.4	2.0	3.5	2.9
7.2	2.9	3.0	2.9
9.0	3.2	2.5	2.7
10.8	3.9	2.0	3.0
12.6	6.1	1.5	3.0
[MB] = 3.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[TGA] = 7.2 × 10 ⁻³ M	
[HCl] = 10.0 × 10 ⁻² M		[HCl] = 10.0 × 10 ⁻² M	
[RuCl ₃] = 2.83 × 10 ⁻⁷ M		[RuCl ₃] = 2.83 × 10 ⁻⁷ M	
CH ₃ OH = 5% (v/v)		CH ₃ OH = 5% (v/v)	
I = 10.0 × 10 ⁻² M		I = 10.0 × 10 ⁻² M	
temp. = 30°		temp. = 30°	

The rate increases with increasing [Ru^{III}], but at higher concentrations of the catalyst (*ca.* 2.83 × 10⁻⁷ M), the order in MB gradually decreases (Table 5). The solution of Ru^{III} was prepared by dissolving RuCl₃ in 0.1 M HCl and the solution was standardized²⁹. ΔH*, ΔS* and ΔG* are found to be 41.9 kJ mol⁻¹, -176.8 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 95.5 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Table 5. Rate constant at different [RuCl₃]

[TGA] = 7.2 × 10⁻³ M, [MB] = 3.0 × 10⁻⁵ M, [HCl] = 10.0 × 10⁻² M, CH₃OH = 5% (v/v), I = 30 × 10⁻² M, temp. = 30°

[RuCl ₃] ×10 ⁷ M	k ₁ ×10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k ^{3/4} ×10 ⁵ mol ^{1/4} dm ^{-1/4} s ⁻¹	k ^{1/2} ×10 ⁶ mol ^{1/2} dm ^{-1/2} s ⁻¹
0.71	2.4	-	-
1.41	2.7	-	-
2.11	2.8	-	-
2.83	2.9	-	-
4.25	-	2.4	-
5.67	-	2.6	-
9.92	-	-	2.2
14.10	-	-	2.4
28.30	-	-	4.0

Discussion

Oxidation of cysteine hydrochloride :

Methylene blue exists as protonated species in acidic medium³⁰⁻³⁴ while cysteine is known to form complexes with metal ions³⁵. Further, cupric ions have been frequently used as catalyst for the oxidation of sulfhydryl compounds³⁶ and here too, a complex designated as C is presumed to be formed with Cu^{II} in acidic medium as revealed by IR spectra of cysteine on interaction with Cu^{II} (Fig. 1). It is evident from the spectrum that such an interaction mainly involves the bending vibrational modes of SH group resulting in the

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of (I) cysteine in KBr and (II) cysteine with Cu^{II} in KBr.

distortion of normal square-planar Cu-cysteine complex and this may account for the specific catalytic influence exhibited *in situ* by cupric ions. An interpretation of kinetic data may be given in terms of the participation of Cu^I obtained on reduction of Cu^{II} ion by cysteine but such a possibility is ruled out in the light of the fact that cysteine is easily oxidized in alkaline but not in the acidic medium^{37,38}. Incidentally, Taylor *et al.*³⁸ used Fe^{III} ion as catalyst (*ca.* 10⁻⁴ M) which has a relatively higher oxidation potential than Cu^{II} ion. Moreover, it has also been recorded in developing analytical procedures for quantitative determination of sulfhydryl compounds with Cu^{II} that the metal ion oxidized thiols quantitatively at higher concentrations and at low concentrations, mainly mercaptides are formed³⁹⁻⁴¹.

It may also be stated here that even in alkaline medium, Cu^{II} ions have been used as catalyst (*ca.* 10⁻⁵ – 10⁻⁷ M) in the oxidation of cysteine of molecular oxygen⁴² and the authors explained the reaction mechanism by postulating the participation of Cu^{II}-cysteine-O₂ complex and from EPR spectroscopic data, they showed that 100 ± (2%) of Cu is present as Cu^{II}. This obviously rules out the possibility of Cu^I acting as catalyst in the reaction system. It may also be mentioned that copper-cysteine complex prepared externally when added to the system, did not catalyze the reaction. Incidentally, the existence of reactive species eluding an easy stereochemical interpretation has been pointed out in these reaction systems and such species have been termed as activated intermediates³⁹. Thus,

The protonated species MBH^+ is presumed to react with cysteine molecule to form thiyl and semireduced methylene blue (HM^\bullet) radicals,

It may be mentioned here that the oxidation of thiols to disulfide has been widely reported to involve RS^\bullet radical⁴³ while the formation of semireduced methylene blue radical (analogous to semiquinone radicals⁴⁴) by the action of reducing substrates such as ascorbic acid on MB has been reported in literature⁴⁵. The participation of free radicals in this reaction system has been qualitatively confirmed by the positive polymerization test with acrylonitrile⁴⁶.

The semireduced methylene blue radical interacts with the copper-cysteine complex to give the leucobase and the dimerization of RS^\bullet radicals may give the disulfide,

The rate of reaction for the above scheme would be given by the rate expression,

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{MBH}^+][\text{RSH}] - k_{-1}[\text{RS}^\bullet][\text{HM}^\bullet][\text{H}^+] \quad (7)$$

On presuming steady state for HM^\bullet and RS^\bullet ,

$$[\text{HM}^\bullet] = \frac{k_1[\text{RSH}][\text{MBH}^+]}{k_{-1}[\text{RS}^\bullet][\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{C}]} \quad (8)$$

On substituting $[\text{HM}^\bullet]$ in eqn. (7),

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{RSH}][\text{MBH}^+] \left[\frac{k_2[\text{C}]}{k_{-1}[\text{RS}^\bullet][\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{C}]} \right] \quad (9)$$

For evaluating $[\text{RS}^\bullet]$, the cubic equation,

$$k_{-1}k_3[\text{RS}^\bullet]^3[\text{H}^+] + k_2k_3[\text{C}][\text{RS}^\bullet]^2 - 2k_1k_2[\text{C}][\text{RSH}][\text{MBH}^+] = 0 \quad (10)$$

was transformed to the standard form,

$$P_3(x) = a_3x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_1x + a_0 = 0 \quad (11)$$

The real root of x represented by x_1 is given by^{47,48}

$$x_1 = -\frac{a_2}{3a_3} \left[\sqrt[3]{\sqrt{(P^3 + Q^2) - Q^{1/3}} - \sqrt{(P^3 + Q^2) + Q^{1/3}}} \right] \quad (12)$$

where,

$$P = \frac{a_1}{3a_3} - \left(\frac{a_2}{a_3} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

and

$$Q = \frac{1}{2a_3} \left(a_0 - \frac{a_2^3}{27a_3^2} - a_2P \right) \quad (14)$$

On substituting $a_1 = 0$ and presuming $P^3 \rightarrow 0$ under the conditions $k_{-1}[\text{H}^+] \gg k_2[\text{C}]$,

$$x_1 = -\frac{a_2}{3a_3} + (-2Q)^{1/3} \quad (15)$$

and

$$Q = \frac{1}{2a_3} \left(a_0 - \frac{a_2^3}{27a_3^2} \right) \quad (16)$$

On substituting the values of a_3 , a_2 and a_0 from eqn. (10),

$$Q = - \left[\frac{a[\text{C}][\text{RSH}][\text{MBH}^+][\text{H}^+] + (k_2k_3[\text{C}])^3}{2 \times 27(k_{-1}k_3[\text{H}^+])^3} \right] \quad (17)$$

where,

$$a = 27 \times 2k_1k_2k_{-1}k_3^2$$

or,

$$[\text{RS}^\bullet] = \frac{a[\text{C}][\text{RSH}][\text{MBH}^+][\text{H}^+]^2 + (k_2k_3[\text{C}])^3}{27(k_{-1}k_3[\text{H}^+])} \quad (18)$$

(Under the condition, $k_{-1}[\text{H}^+] \gg k_2[\text{C}]$).

Thus, on substituting $[\text{MBH}^+] = K_1[\text{MB}][\text{H}^+]$ and

$$[\text{C}] = K_2K_3[\text{RSH}][\text{Cu}^{II}][\text{H}^+],$$

$$\text{or } -\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} =$$

$$\frac{b[\text{RSH}]^2[\text{MB}][\text{H}^+][\text{Cu}^{II}]}{a'[\text{MB}][\text{Cu}^{II}][\text{H}^+]^4 + (b'[\text{RSH}][\text{Cu}^{II}][\text{H}^+]^3)^{1/3}} \quad (19)$$

where $a' = aK_1K_2K_3$, $b = 3k_1k_2k_3K_1K_2K_3$ and $b' = k_2k_3K_2K_3$

$$\text{or, } -\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = \frac{b[\text{RSH}]^{1.3}[\text{MB}][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{H}^+]}{[a'][\text{MB}][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{H}^+] + [\text{RSH}](b'[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}])^{1.3}} \quad (20)$$

At relatively smaller concentrations of cysteine, $[\text{RS}^\bullet]$ is expected to be smaller in eqn. (9) and this explains a first order kinetics in cysteine and MB under these conditions. When $[\text{RS}^\bullet]$ becomes appreciably larger then eqn. (19) becomes tenable and the reaction exhibits a near first order kinetics in cysteine, a fractional order in MB, as well as with respect to hydrogen and cupric ions. It is also seen from eqn. (9) that at low $[\text{MB}]$, there will be a greater probability of recombination of RS^\bullet and in HM^\bullet in step (4) which will result in a larger magnitude of k_{-1} . This will tend to decrease $k_{1/2}$ with decreasing $[\text{MB}]$ as has been noticed. In fact, the transition in order in MB from unity to half at larger $[\text{Cy}]$ or at low $[\text{MB}]$ may be attributed to the larger value of k_{-1} under these conditions but complex nature of the chemical reaction does not permit an easy interpretation for this phenomenon. The proposed reaction scheme also explains the levelling of rate at higher $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. The proposed reaction scheme suggests that the equilibrium (3) will lie far to the left under aerobic conditions due to prevalence of Cu^{II} and this will hamper the reaction given in step (5). This will lead to a first order kinetics even at low concentrations of MB and this postulate has been corroborated by studying the effect of variation of $[\text{MB}]$ as shown in Table 6. This evidently justifies the proposed theoretical treatment of the rate data.

Oxidation of 2-mercaptoethylamine hydrochloride :

The plausible reaction mechanism arrived at on the basis of experimental findings postulates the formation of Cu^{II} -2-ME coordination compound, presumably a square-planar complex, represented subsequently as C,

The existence of such coordination compounds of Cu^{II} with sulfhydryl compounds and nucleic acids has been widely reported in literature^{35,49}. It is also known that methylene blue is protonated in acidic medium^{30,34} and is excited to the triplet state⁵⁰. It seems that triplet state being relatively long-lived in anaerobic conditions, may form a dimer (D) with another methylene blue molecule as reported earlier⁵¹. The coordination complex C is presumed to react with the dimer to produce a transient species (C^*) which may dissociate to give RS^\bullet and HM^\bullet radicals. Thus,

Scheme A

The participation of free radicals was qualitatively confirmed by the polymerization of vinyl acetate as reported earlier⁴⁶.

Table 6. Rate constant of the reaction of cysteine hydrochloride (excess) at different $[\text{MB}]$

$[\text{Cy}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HCl}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{CuSO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $I = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, temp. = 35°

$[\text{MB}]$ $\times 10^5 \text{ M}$	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
3.50	2.9
3.00	3.1
2.50	3.0
2.00	2.9
1.50	3.2
1.25	3.2

It seems that the interaction of the square-planar complex C and the dimer D, which may have a distorted symmetry of anthracene ring, as suggested in the photochemical dimerization of anthracene due to the occupation of antibonding π orbital, is not easily facilitated. Thus, step (23) may be the rate-limiting step and hence,

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{C}][\text{D}] - k_{-1}[\text{C}^*][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{MB}] \quad (27)$$

On applying steady state treatment for C^* and substituting $[\text{C}] = K_2'[\text{RSH}][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}]$ and $[\text{D}] = K_2K_3'[\text{MB}]^2[\text{H}^+]$, the rate of reaction under anaerobic conditions is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1k_2k_1k_2k_3[\text{MB}]^2[\text{RSH}][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{H}^+]}{k_{-1}[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{MB}] + k_2} \quad (28)$$

If $k_2 \gg k_{-1}[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{MB}]$, eqn. (9) can be expressed as

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = k_1K_1K_2'K_3'[\text{MB}]^2[\text{RSH}][\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}][\text{H}^+] \quad (29)$$

Eqn. (29) explains the second order kinetics in MB as has been observed at low [2-ME] under anaerobic conditions. This postulate seems logical because under these conditions, the radicals RS^\bullet and HM^\bullet may not be trapped by molecular oxygen and hence, the concentration of the transient complex C^* must be larger which would give a larger value of k_2 .

On the contrary, k_2 should be smaller under aerobic conditions and the reaction then follows a first order kinetics in MB under such conditions. It is also implied that the dimer (D) being sterically more strained should be more reactive, while under aerobic conditions the triplet MB cation may be quenched by singlet oxygen as reported for anthracene⁵² and this would hamper the formation of dimer. Thus, the interaction of the coordination complex (C) with the protonated species MBH^+ would be more favored as shown in Scheme B.

Scheme B

The participation of RS^\bullet and HM^\bullet may be analogous to that shown in Scheme A. This interpretation seems logical because the enthalpy of activation under aerobic conditions is found to be appreciably larger (49.2 kJ mol^{-1}).

The rate of reaction (Scheme B) will be given by

$$-\frac{d[MB]}{dt} = k_1[C][MBH^+] - k_{-1}[C'][Cu^{II}][H^+] \quad (32)$$

On applying steady treatment for C^* and substituting the values of $[C]$ and $[MBH^+]$, the rate expression is given by

$$-\frac{d[MB]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 K_1 K_2 [RSH][Cu^{II}][MB][H^+]}{k_1 [Cu^{II}][H^+]} \quad (33)$$

The proposed reaction scheme thus predicts a first order kinetics in the substrate as well as in MB (Table 7) and a fractional order in hydrogen ion and Cu^{II} under aerobic

Table 7. Rate constants at different [2-ME] under aerobic conditions
 $[MB] = 3.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[CuSO_4] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $I = 7.508 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $CH_3OH = 5\% \text{ (v/v)}$, $\text{temp.} = 35^\circ$

[2-ME] $\times 10^2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	k_1 $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	k_2 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.07	3.1	–
1.43	4.2	–
1.80	4.0	–
2.20	–	19.5

condition.

A comparison of rate expressions (28) and (33) indicates that the rate should show a linear dependence on $[H^+]$ under anaerobic conditions while a fractional dependence on $[H^+]$ should be noticed under aerobic conditions. In fact, the dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ under both conditions has been found to be complex but in adherence to Schemes A and B, the index of proportionality is almost equal to unity (0.9) under anaerobic conditions while a fractional dependence (0.4) is observed under aerobic conditions at lower concentrations of H^+ ions ($ca. < 4.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) thus justifying the proposed reaction schemes. The reaction schemes, however, suffer from a lacuna vis-a-vis the effect of variation of $[H^+]$ on the rate. The rate shows an optimum while the schemes predict only the accelerating behavior of hydrogen ions on the rate. This may be explained in terms of the chromophoric nature of methylene blue molecule which is known to have a higher redox potential at lower pH ⁵³. The electron density on the trivalent N atom at *meta*-position will be greater owing to the presence of electron-repelling methyl group and thus on increasing $[H^+]$, it may be protonated minimizing the mesomeric effect which would enhance the quinonoid character of MB and will increase the rate. On further increasing $[H^+]$, N atom at *para*-position may be protonated and quinonoid character may partly decrease which would result in decreasing the rate and thus, the rate shows an optimum. Incidentally, our observations with substrates such as *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid interacting with MB confirm this view⁵⁴ and the explanation is similar to the one put forth for explaining pH optima found in enzyme catalyzed reactions⁵⁵.

Oxidation of mercaptoacetic acid :

In Ru^{III} catalyzed reaction, the spectral studies (Figs. 2 and 3) reveal that TGA is coordinated with Ru^{III} *inter alia* the functional carboxyl and sulfhydryl groups to form a transient coordination compound (C') perhaps having an octahedral geometry as generally reported^{56,57}. Moreover, there is a likelihood that Ru^{III} may be coordinated with H_2O ligand which may facilitate the formation of C' in a rate-determining step as reported⁵⁸. This postulate is well supported by a larger value of $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ observed for the catalyzed reaction.

The appearance of a new band at 1270 cm^{-1} also confirms Ru^{III} -TGA interaction because C=S stretch in this region⁵⁹ is ruled out in TGA mainly due to the insignificance of thiol-thione equilibrium. Moreover, the absence of vibrational band around 1800 cm^{-1} when the reaction mixture is scanned after completion of the reaction underlines the fact that TGA weakly interacts with Ru^{III} through C=O

Fig. 3. IR spectrum of TGA with Ru^{III} in KBr.

moiety and perhaps the transient complex C' undergoes dissociation at this site to facilitate the formation of the end-products. It is well established that the coordination compounds of ruthenium show tautomeric equilibrium⁶⁰, which may account for the specific electron transfer reaction between TGA and MB *inter alia* Ru^{III} and form the reactive C^* as shown earlier. Thus,

The radicals HM^\bullet and RS^\bullet may further react with TGA

molecules to produce the end-products as shown earlier. Thus, the rate of reaction will be given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = k_3'''[\text{C}^*] \quad (37)$$

The steady state treatment for species C' and C^* leads to

$$-\frac{d[\text{MB}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1'''k_2'''k_3'''K[\text{MB}][\text{RSH}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+]}{k_2'''k_3'''K[\text{MB}][\text{H}^+] + k_{-1}'''k_{-2}'''[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+] + k_3'''} \quad (38)$$

The rate expression explains a first order kinetics in TGA and a fractional dependence of rate on $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. The transition in order in MB on increasing $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ is also explained in the light of the fact that at higher catalyst concentration the formation of C' will be facilitated which will increase the magnitude of k_2' and show a fractional order in MB.

Conclusion :

The kinetics of the reaction of methylene blue with 2-mercaptoethylamine hydrochloride catalyzed by Cu^{II} when studied in presence of oxygen reveals that the rate of its oxidation is retarded by molecular oxygen. This is evident from the value of free energy of activation under anaerobic and aerobic conditions (82.0 and 96.3 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively). It is known that 2-ME is the functional part of coenzyme A which regulates the respiration cycle while MB is a polycyclic aromatic compound which are known to be carcinogenic. Thus, oxygen seems to counter the oxidation of 2-ME by carcinogenic polycyclic electron receptors thereby increasing the availability of this substrate for the regulation of respiration cycle. On the other hand, the near constancy of ΔG^* in the catalyzed and non-catalyzed oxidation of TGA indicates that the energetics of the structurally similar cell reactions are not influenced appreciably by Ru^{III} .

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